

Two Journeys: Insights on the Annotation of Large-Scale Optical Music Recognition Datasets

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Abstract. The use of Optical Music Recognition (OMR) requires annotated music scores (ground truth) for training or adaptation. Besides the level of structured encoding, a significant part of the existing OMR methods still needs ground truth also at image level, which is indeed still important for tasks adjacent to OMR. However, annotating images is a major part of OMR project costs: not just the work of the annotators themselves but also associated software development and process management. Unlike most other more prevalent image annotation tasks in industry, in the case of music notation, infrastructure is lacking, and many pitfalls exist. Thus, in this paper, we report on the combined experience of two ongoing OMR projects with major data collection and annotation efforts, and we formulate recommendations for managing music notation annotation projects, leading to efficient use of the inevitably limited resources.

Keywords: Optical Music Recognition · Handwritten music scores · Annotation Software · Ground-truthing · Music Notation Formats

1 Introduction

Optical Music Recognition (OMR) consists of automatically reading images of musical scores into computer-processable formats [6]. One of its main applications is aiding musicologists in the long and demanding process of transcribing a piece. Nevertheless, despite the advances in the field, fully automatic recognition of historical handwritten music scores is extremely difficult due to the high variability in handwriting styles, music notation idiosyncrasies and severe supporting medium degradation. Existing State-of-the-Art OMR methods are based on powerful deep learning architectures, but at the cost of requiring significant amounts of labelled data (ground-truth) to train and to adapt to new music

collections. In this context, it is important to note that it is not enough to provide a scanned music sheet together with the transcription in MusicXML/MEI, because the OMR system needs to learn the position and appearance of each music element in the image.

During the last decades, the OMR community has devoted significant efforts in creating annotated datasets⁶ for music recognition, staff removal, writer identification, etc. But, not surprisingly, the ground-truth of handwritten music scores in Common Western Music Notation (CWMN) is barely available, becoming a bottleneck in the field. Therefore, the annotation of such scores is an essential step for advancing towards robust Optical Music Recognition systems, and to effectively apply them in practice with confidence to handwritten scores. However, ground-truthing is a resource-intensive process: not only in terms of the effort required to create the ground-truth, but also because of the overhead of managing human resources and the whole annotation process.

In this paper, we describe the experience with two ongoing annotation processes^{7,8} of OMR image data: the first one focuses on coarse annotations, whereas the second one focuses on fine-grained annotations. We describe the associated project priorities, the resulting trade-offs, the annotation tools and workflows, and the “user experience” from both the perspective of the annotators, annotation management, and project management. Although we do not make specific recommendations, from the discussion of the advantages and disadvantages of our approaches, we provide experience from extensive projects to help others with designing their own data collection efforts.

2 Previous Work

Very few projects focus on music annotation for OMR. A significant portion of modern-day OMR efforts are focused on older music written in square and Mensural notation, which have been the focus of large-scale projects: SIMSSA [10] and PolifonIA [16]. Previous works on this notation system resulted in the incorporation of datasets such as SEILS [23], or CAPITAN [8].

For scores in Common Western Music Notation (CWMN), large-scale transcription efforts have been less frequent. Most modern datasets are sourced from existing typeset transcriptions of music, which are usually adapted to a specific OMR-related task following specific design goals. The DeepScores dataset [28] and its V2 successor [29] are built for music object detection. They include symbol-level detection and segmentation annotations. The GrandStaff dataset [25] sources the KernScores⁹ repository to build a dataset of piano-form sheet music encoded in `**KERN` format for performing page-level end-to-end recognition. The DoReMi Dataset [26] is a collection of classical works engraved using

⁶ <https://apacha.github.io/OMR-Datasets/>

⁷ The Project on Music scores at the CVC: <https://pages.cvc.uab.es/musiccores/>

⁸ The OmniOMR project at Charles University and Moravian Library <https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/grants/omniomr>.

⁹ <https://kern.ccarh.org/>

Dorico that incorporates transcriptions and annotations for most of the widely-adopted formats. Other common sources of scores for OMR dataset creation include the OpenScore project [11], a corpus of classic public domain music works engraved by the MuseScore community, [15] produced by Hentschel *et al.*, a large corpus of transcribed scores for musicological analysis and the PDMX dataset [17], the largest collection of MusicXML files to date.

For handwritten scores, dataset construction projects almost always require the intervention of human annotators. The most widely known large-scale music annotation project produced the MUSCIMA++ Dataset [13], which was built atop the existing CVC-MUSCIMA writer identification and staff removal dataset [9]. This dataset contains 140 pages with highly-detailed segmentation annotations and their relationships encoded using a custom graph-based format. Smaller datasets include the Pau Llinàs collection from Baró *et al.* [2], which contains only a few hundred measure-level samples. There are also a few symbol-level datasets such as HOMUS [7], which is primarily intended for Online music recognition but can be used for offline OMR by rasterising pen strokes.

Most of these datasets are developed using different conventions and requirements and it is not surprising that they are mostly incompatible. No encoding seems to suit all of the needs of the entirety of the community. Furthermore, experience in manually annotating large-scale OMR datasets is limited.

3 OMR Annotation Process Design

Designing good OMR image annotation pipelines is a complex endeavour. Indeed, the requirements will vary depending on the exact needs of the final user, the ergonomic requirements for the transcribers, the OMR method (or methods) the dataset is designed to accommodate and the resources available for the production of the dataset. In particular, the OMR method to be applied has a direct implication on the level of annotation detail, the amount of data to be produced and the format in which the data will be presented. Moreover, the timeline and resources available for this ground-truth creation process condition whether or not the development of specific customized annotation software is possible.

Format. Most current music notation formats are designed to interface with music engraving software, which tend to prioritise semantic encodings rather than literal representations of scores. This is a sensible choice to support the musician, as it will prevent the writing of unsound scores and use their knowledge of the language to their advantage to accelerate the engraving process. Nevertheless, this poses problems for the OMR practitioner, as most widespread formats – and, by extension, music engraving tools – represent music scores in a non-explicit, non-exhaustive manner [27]. In particular, MusicXML hides many details about the layout of the score, which are abstracted within music concepts e.g. Key signatures are usually represented by the number of fifths required to get to a specific Sharp/Flat configuration, not by modelling the position of each accidental separately. In some engravers, the position of each Accidental might change with the same key. The MEI format allows a more literal style

of transcription, but we have found it to be significantly less well-supported on WYSIWYG transcription software necessary for making the detailed encodings. Moreover, the available conversion scripts from MEI to other formats seem to be unreliable. Therefore, we have found it not possible to rely on existing representations of music alone.

Custom software development. One of the key requirements of modern-day OMR is incorporating symbol-level annotations [6,30]. Mainstream music engraving software does not support this feature. Thus, it is necessary to design either a collection of supporting file formats that allow annotating this information in parallel to existing ones or creating one full music representation that powers all aspects of OMR-oriented music notation. Implementing a full music notation system requires having a solution to engrave, convert and edit these scores, which is a non-trivial engineering effort. On the other hand, while relying on existing tools has the advantage of not requiring as much new software, coordinating them can be complex, both for the implementers and for the annotators.

Targeted OMR System. There exist different types of OMR systems. End-to-end models can train using only image transcriptions extracted at the line level [2] or the page level [25]. On the other hand, pipeline or graph-based methods [3] usually require an object detection or segmentation step, for which fine-grained annotations for each symbol are additionally required for training.

Level of annotation detail. Annotating music primitives amounts to hundreds or thousands of annotations per page, which is very costly. A possible solution is to use loosely annotated symbols in order to reduce this manual labor burden. The solutions presented in this work explore two options in this regard: one produces fewer, precisely annotated samples and the other produces more, yet less precisely annotated images.

These are the most important decisions, but the list is far from exhaustive. Depending on the need, the expected OMR method to be applied, and available resources, one should opt for one of these choices. Next, we describe two different annotation processes and discuss their advantages and disadvantages.

4 Process 1: Coarse Annotations

The first annotation process consists of a coarse annotation of the music scores. Concretely, the objective is to provide a bounding-box for each music element, together with its corresponding MusicXML category. The priority is to speed-up the process, labelling more pages with less human resources.

4.1 Annotation Pipeline 1

The coarse pipeline has two steps. The first step consists in the transcription of the music score using MuseScore [1], obtaining a MusicXML as output. The second step consists in the alignment of the MusicXML with the image, providing the bounding-boxes of each element. In this step, we have specifically designed

an Android application for a Tablet with stylus pen. Figure 1 shows a summary of this first annotation pipeline. These steps are described next.

Fig. 1. The coarse annotation pipeline. In green, steps that are assisted by human transcribers. In blue, automated steps.

Transcription The process begins by assigning a score scan to a musicologist, who transcribes it using MuseScore 4.4 [1]. This transcription is performed as literally as possible – akin to an *urtext* edition. Each line of music is stored in a separate transcription file, with *line* being understood as *any set of staves that are written to be played in unison or that belong to the same instrument*, as seen in partellas, orchestral works or pianoform music. For instance, in orchestral works, all instruments that belong to the same line are written into the same file using different parts. On the other hand, for single-instrument works, each of the lines on the same page are annotated in a different file. These files are uniquely identified by the vertical position of the transcribed material. Key semantic information such as the part’s Clef, Time Signature and Key are always inserted at the beginning of each line in order to guarantee that the original full score can be reconstructed, but in those cases where they are not explicitly written in the score they are set to be hidden.

Once the MuseScore files for all lines of a page are obtained, they are converted to MusicXML automatically using MuseScore’s batch conversion system. This line-based transcription process is chosen to guarantee that the layout of the original score is respected when processing the material using any MusicXML engraver – even those that do not fully support the format’s layout features – and to facilitate some downstream alignment steps.

We have chosen to distribute MusicXML as the base format for our work because of better tooling support and because of its more extended use. However, in order to enable the future possibility of generating MEI or even MNX, we have chosen to also distribute the original MuseScore files with the dataset once it is ready. Given how the alignment pipeline works, we anticipate that adding such support alignment for MEI down the line would be quite straight-forward.

MusicXML-to-Image Alignment In order to align each musical symbol in the MusicXML with its representation in the image, a second intervention by the musicologist is required. For this task, we have designed an application that runs on an Android tablet with a stylus pen, since the labelling process is significantly faster and more accurate than using a computer with a mouse input.

In order to perform the symbol-level alignment, the music objects need to be given some form of identification to assign them a bounding box. This is fairly trivial for those objects that MusicXML models explicitly and provides an `id` attribute for – e.g. Clefs or Barlines. We generate procedural IDs automatically for these objects after the transcription process. However, there are many objects that either do not have this `id` attribute or whose MusicXML definitions map to multiple-object compounds. We identify these objects using the `id` of their parent object and some form of disambiguation name for that specific element. Each symbol is related with their graphical representation in the score by leveraging the hierarchical primitive representation produced by the Verovio [24] engraving system. We have authored a fork ¹⁰ which inserts our generated identifiers in the output SVG, enabling the relationships between MusicXML and score representations. For those cases where Verovio’s primitive definitions do not match ours or the identifiers cannot be easily inserted within the engraving, a post-processing script inserts the missing information after-the-fact on the SVG directly.

Once this decorated SVG file is produced, musicologists are tasked to label each of the desired symbols by drawing a rough circle around them using a stylus pen on an Android tablet. A screenshot of the main alignment screen of the Android app is shown in Figure 2. The application uses the rendered score’s SVG class information to select the symbols of interest, changes their colour and the user selects its matching symbol in the real image. Then, using the symbol’s ID stored in the SVG the final output alignment is generated. Only the final file containing the relationships between object bounding boxes and identifiers is necessary, which we have encoded as a slightly modified COCO format file (string-based IDs are used instead of integers). With this identifier, the XPath to the original MusicXML nodes can be constructed.

4.2 User Experience: Annotation Process 1

One senior musicologist has managed the workload of the eight musicologists that have worked in this coarse annotation process, obtaining more than 1.300 pages in less than one year. Concerning quality control, each page has been fully transcribed by one annotator and revised by another.

The time required by an expert user to transcribe a handwritten music page into MuseScore in the style demanded by this method varies depending on several factors such as the number of staves per system or the variety of instruments involved. On average, transcription takes approximately 50 minutes per page, with a typical range between 30 and 90 minutes. In contrast, alignment usually

¹⁰ <https://github.com/ptorras/verovio.git>, `ident` branch.

Fig. 2. Screenshot of the Alignment Android application. At the top, the real handwritten document being annotated. At the bottom, its transcription. In green, objects that have already been annotated. In yellow, objects that have been skipped. In this example, the time signature is not present in the original document and thus it has not been annotated.

takes less time, averaging around 30 minutes per page, although for pages containing large numbers of systems (ranging from 6 to 12 staves), alignment time can sometimes double.

The alignment application in the Android tablet offers fast performance and responds promptly to input from the digital stylus pen, contributing to an efficient and precise user experience. Its interface is intuitive and user-friendly, facilitating navigation and task execution without requiring extensive prior training. The app facilitates alignment in multiple sessions and correcting previously aligned segments via discretionary auto-saving.

Some downsides of the design of the application are that neither the image display nor the Verovio transcription automatically adjust to the position of the cursor. This shortcoming hinders precise task tracking, especially on pages with a high number of systems, where it is easy to lose visual reference of the current working point (hence the increase in alignment time for multi-staff scores). This is a result of having a horizontally-optimised view for the workspace.

A key limitation of this workflow is error correction. If transcription errors are identified during the alignment phase, the process must be paused, and the corresponding line must be revised in MuseScore before the alignment can continue. It is important to note that if a correction in MuseScore involves the addition or deletion of elements, misalignment will occur in the app from that point forward. This happens because Verovio identifiers shift to account for newly added elements or the removal of existing ones. Consequently, the alignment of the affected line must be temporarily halted. In contrast, when the correction consists only of a substitution (e.g., replacing one note with another), the identifiers

remain unchanged. In such cases, the alignment can proceed as normal once the updated SVG file is loaded, since the alignment remains unaffected.

Transcription errors are relatively frequent, with approximately 21% of lines containing at least one error on their first pass. Most errors are detected during the reviewing phase, but some can remain. This rate can be reduced through multiple rounds of revision, at the cost of more human resources. Nevertheless, it should be acknowledged that due to the double conversion of the original MuseScore (.mscz) files—first to MusicXML and then to SVG via Verovio—errors may still arise during the alignment stage due to format limitations. For this reason, it is essential that error correction remains possible in this final phase.

5 Process 2: Fine-grained Annotation

The objective of this process is to obtain a dataset of 1000 pages with fine-grained, very accurate annotation. This can then serve both as a comprehensive difficult benchmark representative of the variety of scores found in a large library collection, and as training data for systems targeting such a domain. It is also intended to serve as a seed dataset for large-scale realistic music notation synthesis [22]: with a sufficiently broad collection of annotated scores, many different out-of-domain conditions for new collections can be simulated. The dataset should also enable comparing the performance of end-to-end and object detection based OMR pipelines on a real-world collection. For this reason, the dataset is intended to contain two layers: the Music Notation Graph (MuNG) that annotates the score image itself [13], and in parallel its MusicXML representation.

5.1 Annotation Tools 2

Obtaining the MusicXML layer of data was unproblematic: we simply use MuseScore [1]. We adapt transcription rules used by the OpenScore Lieder project [12]. Each page was transcribed by one annotator and revised by another. This process was straightforward, with average speeds under 2 hours per page, including the complete revision.

The annotation toolchain for MuNG has proven much more troublesome. The MuNG format was originally designed and implemented in the MUSCIMA++ dataset [13] and had an annotation tool: MUSCIMarker [14]. However, due to lack of maintenance, MUSCIMarker has become unusable, as the features of the Python GUI Framework kivy it relies on have since been deprecated. Additionally, the all-Python implementation would have been difficult to transfer into the online environment, which we identified as necessary for process management. Meanwhile, many commercial tools for image annotation have become available.

Thus, faced with the choice between rewriting an old tool and using an existing interface with workflow management implemented, a Python SDK, and a sufficiently permissive academic licence, we decided to rather allocate software development resources to actual recognition rather than annotation tooling, and started using Labelbox for MuNG annotation.

Fig. 3. The workflow of fine-grained annotation process. Two separate paths for each ground truth type: MuNG (upper) and MusicXML (lower). Because the manual steps are done in one step separately for each ground truth layer, less automation was needed (though some symbol disambiguation is needed in the conversion from Labelbox outputs to MuNG format). Manual steps in green, automated in blue. Note that completing the MuNG path took approx. 5x longer than MusicXML path.

Labelbox in principle did support this process. The only adjustment compared to MUSCIMA++ was that while the Labelbox annotation interface for images does support natively adding links between objects, this is only supported for polygons and polylines that have defined control points. We therefore defined the ontology to use polygons instead of pixel masks for all symbols except stafflines and thin barlines, which were annotated as polylines. The complete ontology has 62 different elements, of which 3 are edges (syntax, precedence, and staff placement).

Seven annotators worked on the process. All had significant musical experience: professionals or students, primarily from the early music community due to a greater familiarity with understanding musical manuscripts (a large portion of the annotated collection comes from the 17th and 18th centuries). Each image was fully annotated by one annotator, and a different annotator would review it. Two annotation managers shared the workload of making sure the process ran smoothly. GitHub discussions were used to build up institutional knowledge, both on MuNG annotation policies and on optimal use of Labelbox. It took approx. 5 months to get to a point where the policies for both were largely complete and only rare situations needed discussion as they came up.¹¹

Labelbox makes the annotations available via an API in its own JSON format. We convert these to MuNG format with a script. Compared to MUSCIMA++, we made several changes to the annotation policy to make the manual process easier: this mostly concerned merging several names into one and disambiguating them automatically afterwards. Most importantly, we only use one `flag` class instead of splitting it into `flag8thUp`, `flag8thDown`, etc., because Labelbox had poor support for keyboard shortcuts to select an object class.

¹¹ These keep coming up at roughly 1-2 per month.

The overall workflow is shown in 3. The workflow is structured so that the manual steps are kept together at the start of both annotation paths, so that changes in the automated part of the pipeline do not necessitate revisiting manually performed steps.

5.2 User Experience: Toolchain 2

While Labelbox in principle supported the functionality we needed, it had significant issues in “quality of life”. It does not support tracking how annotators work: this is important to distinguish between first round of annotation and review and to find inefficiencies in the process. Labelbox also has only limited keyboard shortcuts. In September 2024, Labelbox removed the autosave feature without warning. Even such fundamentals as data export proved problematic: at one point Labelbox silently changed their back-end in a way that made larger annotations run into server-side CPython recursion limits. This, and other unexpected behaviours, are documented on the Labelbox platform piecemeal. In the end, it proved easier to manage assignment of images to annotators through an external google sheet.

More importantly, the image annotation UI slowed down significantly as objects and relationships were added onto an image. Above 2000 annotated objects (which amounts to a third of all pages) the lag was 2–4 seconds per UI action. It became apparent that annotating this many polygons and relationships in a single image is beyond the capability of Labelbox.

All these issues, combined with the annotation already being difficult, meant that the total average time per image (including revision) was approx. 11 hours, even after the workflow was optimised. This was not acceptable.

5.3 Toolchain 2: Search for alternatives

In the search for alternatives, we had to relax the condition for native support of relationships between objects. The next two choices were Label Studio¹² and CVAT¹³. Tests with annotators showed that smoother workflow management and better keyboard shortcuts could cut down annotation time by approx. 20 % in CVAT. In contrast to Label Studio, CVAT natively supported polylines, which could be used as “poor man’s edges”.¹⁴

While it is possible to use polylines and edges and estimating the objects to which edges should be attached from the endpoints’ positions (and potentially polyline classes), this becomes a significant issue for quality control. Because of how flexible the MuNG format must be to cover the flexibility of music notation, it would be very difficult to automatically determine whether an endpoint is

¹² <https://labelstud.io/>

¹³ <https://www.cvat.ai/>

¹⁴ Label Studio supports relationships in its data model, but the UI for this functionality is only designed for text annotation, not for images. Though Label Studio is open-source, the programming effort to implement this for images was prohibitive, as it would have involved changes in the software’s rendering core.

misplaced. Disambiguating endpoint attachment in situations where objects significantly overlap is also difficult. Given that the speed-up in annotation when moving to CVAT was not radical, and that CVAT also started experiencing noticeable lag above 750 objects, we determined the risk associated with data quality was not worth the speed-up.

The only viable solution proved to be exactly what we initially set out to avoid: implementing a specialised tool [21], currently being rolled out to annotators.

6 Discussion and Conclusions

What can we learn from these two different but extensive experiences with OMR ground truth creation?

Do extensive risk assessment. Both processes ran into significant delays. In both cases, this was likely due to insufficient risk assessment, even though both teams had extensive prior experience with dataset creation. Process 1 underestimated the time both for annotation and for quality control and revisions, and underestimated time needed for bugs and error correction in the Android software. Process 2 avoided delays connected to SW development and was thus able to scale annotation quickly, but ran into severe inefficiency with unsuitable annotation tools (Labelbox), and in the end had to commit to software development anyway. Thus, we recommend doing a full-scale pilot annotation of several pages before fully committing to a process.

Ensure resources and timelines for software development. Music notation is a specific domain that is not served sufficiently by existing image annotation tools. Even MusicXML must be adapted to meet the needs of OMR annotation processes. MuNG is a better format but lacks the software infrastructure to be broadly useful (for instance: conversion to MusicXML), and its annotation is difficult (though its pixel-wise mask requirement can of course be relaxed for more coarse-grained annotation). One should always assume that software development will be necessary — at least contributing to maintenance of open-source solutions.

User interfaces are key. The stylus-based annotation of Process 1 is so far the most efficient method for marking areas in sheet music images, together with the original MuReT tablet-based tool [8]. The in-browser nature of the new MuNG-centered tools in Process 2 [21] is a step towards leveraging this possibility. Process 2 was hindered by suboptimally implemented user interfaces of 3rd-party tools. Not just the different target quality level (coarse vs. fine-grained image annotation), but the level of effort towards improving user interfaces — and the control over the toolchain that made such effort possible — is the main reason why Process 1 was able to annotate much faster than Process 2.

Consider implications of methods for dataset building. The issues with sheet music image annotations are also a strong argument for relying more on end-to-end methods, where only the non-problematic transcriptions to MusicXML would have to be done in both projects. (De)linearisation for MusicXML

is also already handled with the LMX format [20], and it can be converted to ****`(be)`kern** as well [25]. Compared to the commodification of object detection (e.g. the YOLO platform), however, end-to-end methods are more difficult to train and so they move risk into a different stage of a complete OMR project. Due to missing resources for object detection, no systematic comparison of end-to-end and detection-based methods for OMR has been performed so far, so this trade-off is hard to evaluate at this time.

Engage with the OMR community. Although the situation with OMR datasets continues to improve (recently e.g. a benchmark for end-to-end recognition [18], data for medieval paleography [4] and jazz lead sheets [19]), literature on data creation processes is limited. Thanks to the efforts of venues such as WoRMS, GREC, DLFM, or the `OMR-research` website¹⁵ and github¹⁶, the field of OMR is now more of a community than before [5]: it is advisable to leverage these venues as opportunities to discuss dataset building processes, and to attach as much importance to discussing data as to recognition systems themselves.

OMR remains an important capability for digital musicology and music libraries, but despite recent advances, ground truth creation is far from over. While deep learning has brought viable methods for satisfactorily resolving OMR, these require large and representative enough labelled data to be applicable in production — and the incredible diversity of musical scores means that domain adaptation remains a challenge. Dataset creation thus remains an important element of any OMR project for the foreseeable future. We hope that by sharing our combined experience of two such significant ground truth creation efforts, we will help potential users apply advances in OMR state-of-the-art, and to bring this capability to sheet music users everywhere.

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¹⁵ <https://omr-research.net/>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/omr-research>

References

1. MuseScore Studio 4.4. MuseScore (Nov 24)
2. Baró, A., Badal, C., Fornés, A.: Handwritten Historical Music Recognition by Sequence-to-Sequence with Attention Mechanism. In: 2020 17th International Conference on Frontiers in Handwriting Recognition (ICFHR). pp. 205–210. IEEE Computer Society, Dortmund, Germany (Sep 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICFHR2020.2020.00046>
3. Baró, A., Riba, P., Fornés, A.: Musigraph: Optical music recognition through object detection and graph neural network. In: International Conference on Frontiers in Handwriting Recognition. pp. 171–184. Springer (2022)
4. Bouressa, K., Fujinaga, I.: From pixels to paleography: A dual-pathway neural network for neume script classification. In: Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology. p. 1–9. DLfM '25, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3748336.3748344>
5. Calvo-Zaragoza, J., Hajič, J., Pacha, A.: Discussion group summary: Optical music recognition. In: Fornés, A., Lamiroy, B. (eds.) Graphics Recognition. Current Trends and Evolutions. pp. 152–157. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2018)
6. Calvo-Zaragoza, J., Hajič Jr., J., Pacha, A.: Understanding Optical Music Recognition. *ACM Computing Surveys* **53**(4), 1–35 (Jul 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3397499>
7. Calvo-Zaragoza, J., Oncina, J.: Recognition of Pen-Based Music Notation: The HOMUS Dataset. In: 22nd International Conference on Pattern Recognition. pp. 3038–3043. IEEE Computer Society, Stockholm, Sweden (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPR.2014.524>
8. Calvo-Zaragoza, J., Rizo, D., Iñesta, J.M.: Two (note) heads are better than one: Pen-based multimodal interaction with music scores. In: et al. Devaney, J. (ed.) 17th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference. pp. 509–514. International Society for Music Information Retrieval, New York City (2016)
9. Fornés, A., Dutta, A., Gordo, A., Lladós, J.: CVC-MUSCIMA: A ground truth of handwritten music score images for writer identification and staff removal. *International Journal on Document Analysis and Recognition (IJDAR)* **15**(3), 243–251 (Sep 2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10032-011-0168-2>
10. Fujinaga, I., Hankinson, A.: SIMSSA: Single Interface for Music Score Searching and Analysis. *Journal of the Japanese Society for Sonic Arts* **6**(3), 25–30 (2014)
11. Gotham, M., Jonas, P., Bower, B., Bosworth, W., Rootham, D., VanHandel, L.: Scores of Scores: An Openscore Project to Encode and Share Sheet Music. In: 5th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology. pp. 87–95. ACM, Paris, France (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3273024.3273026>
12. Gotham, M.R.H., Jonas, P.: The OpenScore lieder corpus. In: Music Encoding Conference Proceedings 2021. vol. 1, pp. 131–136. Universidad de Alicante, Alicante, Spain (May 2022)
13. Hajič, J., Pecina, P.: The MUSCIMA++ Dataset for Handwritten Optical Music Recognition. In: 2017 14th IAPR International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR). vol. 01, pp. 39–46. IEEE Computer Society, Kyoto, Japan (Nov 2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDAR.2017.16>
14. Hajič jr., J., Pecina, P.: Groundtruthing (Not Only) Music Notation with MUSICMarker: A Practical Overview. In: 14th International Conference on Docu-

- ment Analysis and Recognition. pp. 47–48. IEEE Computer Society, Kyoto, Japan (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDAR.2017.271>
15. Hentschel, J., Rammos, Y., Neuwirth, M., Rohrmeier, M.: A corpus and a modular infrastructure for the empirical study of (an)notated music. *Scientific Data* **12**(1), 685 (Apr 2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04976-z>
 16. Iñesta Quereda, J.M.: PolifonIA Project. <https://grfia.dlsi.ua.es/polifonia/>
 17. Long, P., Novack, Z., Berg-Kirkpatrick, T., McAuley, J.: PDMX: A Large-Scale Public Domain MusicXML Dataset for Symbolic Music Processing. In: ICASSP 2025 - 2025 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP). pp. 1–5. IEEE Signal Processing Society, Hyderabad, India (Apr 2025). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICASSP49660.2025.10890217>
 18. Martínez-Sevilla, J.C., Cerveto-Serrano, J., Luna, N., Chapman, G., Sapp, C., Rizo, D., Calvo-Zaragoza, J.: Sheet music benchmark: Standardized optical music recognition evaluation (2025), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.10488>
 19. Martínez-Sevilla, J.C., Foscarin, F., Garcia-Iasci, P., Rizo, D., Calvo-Zaragoza, J., Widmer, G.: Optical music recognition of jazz lead sheets (2025)
 20. Mayer, J., Straka, M., Hajič jr., J., Pecina, P.: Practical End-to-End Optical Music Recognition for Pianoform Music (Mar 2024). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.13763>
 21. Mayer, J., Jebavý, F., Herzánová Vlková, M., Dvořáková, M., Pecina, P., Hajič, Jan, J.: Mung studio: Annotation tool for music notation graph. In: Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology. p. 114–118. DLFM '25, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3748336.3748379>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3748336.3748379>
 22. Mayer, J., Pecina, P., Hajič, Jan, J.: Smashcima: Full-page handwritten music document synthesizer. In: Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology. p. 119–123. DLFM '25, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3748336.3748380>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3748336.3748380>
 23. Parada-Cabaleiro, E., Batliner, A., Baird, A., Schuller, B.: The SEILS Dataset: Symbolically Encoded Scores in Modern-Early Notation for Computational Musicology. In: 18th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference. pp. 575–581. International Society for Music Information Retrieval, Suzhou, China (2017)
 24. Pugin, L.: Verovio. <https://www.verovio.org/>
 25. Ríos-Vila, A., Rizo, D., Iñesta, J.M., Calvo-Zaragoza, J.: End-to-end optical music recognition for pianoform sheet music. *International Journal on Document Analysis and Recognition (IJDAR)* **26**(3), 347–362 (Sep 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10032-023-00432-z>
 26. Shatri, E., Fazekas, G.: DoReMi: First glance at a universal OMR dataset. In: Calvo-Zaragoza, J., Pacha, A. (eds.) Proceedings of the 3rd International Workshop on Reading Music Systems. pp. 43–49. Alicante, Spain (2021)
 27. Torras, P., Biswas, S., Fornés, A.: A Unified Representation Framework for the Evaluation of Optical Music Recognition Systems. *International Journal on Document Analysis and Recognition (IJDAR)* **27**(Special issue on “advanced topics in document analysis and recognition”), 379–393 (Jul 2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10032-024-00485-8>
 28. Tuggener, L., Elezi, I., Schmidhuber, J., Pelillo, M., Stadelmann, T.: DeepScores - A Dataset for Segmentation, Detection and Classification of Tiny Objects. In: 24th

- International Conference on Pattern Recognition. pp. 3704–3709. IEEE Computer Society, Beijing, China (2018). <https://doi.org/10.21256/zhaw-4255>
29. Tuggener, L., Satyawan, Y.P., Pacha, A., Schmidhuber, J., Stadelmann, T.: The DeepScoresV2 Dataset and Benchmark for Music Object Detection. In: Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Pattern Recognition. pp. 9188–9195. IEEE Computer Society, Milan, Italy (2020). <https://doi.org/10.21256/zhaw-20647>
 30. Yesilkanat, A., Soullard, Y., Coüasnon, B., Girard, N.: Full-Page Music Symbols Recognition: State-of-the-Art Deep Model Comparison for Handwritten and Printed Music Scores. In: Sfikas, G., Retsinas, G. (eds.) Document Analysis Systems. pp. 327–343. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham (2024). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70442-0_20